

INTRODUCTORY SECTION:

a //show Powerpoint

Hello everyone,

Today I would like to give you a short tutorial on how Citavi 6 works.

Let's start with a brief overview: Citavi is a literature management program that you can use if you're writing a term paper or thesis. In short: Whenever you use literature for research in a paper and need to cite it, a literature management program like Citavi offers you a variety of functions to help you keep an overview - even if you use several hundred sources.

b //show Citavi GUI

One feature is that you can use Citavi to see all your references that belong to a project at a glance,

to display a preview of the file text,

mark and categorize your titles

and search them.

You can also create citations for these titles, which you can then integrate into your own works in Word or LaTeX.

c //show a bibliography as a PDF (does not have to be created with Citavi)

Citavi will then automatically create a bibliography in the citation style you specified.

d //show a concrete, comprehensive example in Citavi GUI

Citavi relieves you of many repetitive tasks that you would otherwise have to do by hand, especially when entering references, and it's easy to make mistakes, for example when entering metadata for a title.

In the case of a scientific article, these are the authors, which may sometimes be 5 or 6 authors, the title, the journal in which the article was published, the volume, the issue, the page numbers and the publication date.

Depending on the citation style, all of these fields need to be filled in.

ADDING LITERATURE SECTION:

In the following, I'll explain the most important features of Citavi and how you can use them to save yourself as much work as possible.

e //show PowerPoint

One of Citavi's most useful features is its OCR functionality (Optical Character Recognition), which means that if you want to add a book or academic article to your references, Citavi can read the contents of the file to get information about the reference. You can give Citavi individual files or several files at once.

f //remain in PowerPoint

There are two outcomes when using this OCR functionality.

Ideally, your file should contain an identifier. For books, this is the ISBN, in 10- or 13-digit format. Citavi recognizes both and can also convert them.

For scientific articles this is

- The DOI or
- the PubMed ID or
- the PubMed Central ID or
- the arXiv ID.

g //remain in PowerPoint

When you submit a PDF file to Citavi, Citavi uses OCR to check if there is such an identifier on the first 5 pages.

When Citavi finds an identifier, it accesses centrally managed online catalogs or databases in which the metadata is entered. The fields filled in this way are expected to be 99.9% correct.

If Citavi cannot find an identifier, it uses the file properties to fill in basic fields. These are often just the title according to the file name and the number of pages according to the number of pages in the file.

h //remain in PowerPoint

Of course, the OCR scan is not necessary if you send Citavi a text file that contains one or more identifiers.

For example, a Word file with literature recommendations from your professor, perhaps containing a few books with ISBNs, but also journal articles with DOIs.

i //show Citavi GUI

I'll show you this again in the Citavi interface.

j //show PDF import with DOI

The easiest way is to drag and drop a title that you have as a PDF into your title list. As already mentioned, this also works for several files at once!

This one has a DOI on the first page, so exactly what I just described happens - Citavi recognizes the DOI, uses online databases for a comparison and the fields are filled in automatically.

The bottom bar is yellow if not all titles in the project are currently displayed, but only the last import or search results, for example.

However, you can always display all titles in the project again by clicking on "Deselect".

k //show PDF import without DOI

And now again for comparison with a PDF in which there is no identifier.

When I drop it into my title list, only the fields whose values Citavi can determine based on the file properties are filled in, i.e. the page numbers and the title, which initially corresponds to the file name.

However, you can easily correct this by copying the correct values from the title preview.

Then click "Deselect" again and you will see the entire project.

l //show Word import

[INCORRECT:] You can do the same with a reference list in Word, like this one, which I formatted horribly on purpose. Simply drag and drop it into the reference list and Citavi will read the identifiers, retrieve the database entries and add the references.

[CORRECT:] You can do something similar with a reference list in Word, like this one, which I formatted horribly on purpose. Citavi can recognize the identifiers, but you have to select the "ISBN, DOI, other ID" function and the "From a file" option instead of drag & drop. All identifiers found are then listed again and can be discarded or accepted. Make sure that the file is not open during this process, otherwise Citavi will have problems accessing it and won't find any identifiers.

Again, do not forget to "deselect" if you are happy with your import and want to see the entire project again.

m

Next, I would like to explain the search and navigation functions.

NAVIGATION AND SEARCH SECTION:

n //show Citavi GUI //skip through titles with arrow keys

If your project is large enough so that the reference overview on the left becomes confusing, Citavi gives you several ways to navigate through your literature and search for specific references.

Of course, as you have just seen, Citavi has metadata for each reference, i.e. title, author, year of publication, etc.

You can search these fields.

o //show PowerPoint

To do this, you must prefix your search query with certain abbreviations so that the search term is only searched for in a specific field.

These are the most important ones.

You can use the abbreviation *a:* to search for names of people, i.e. authors, editors, contributors, etc. The abbreviation *d* searches your titles by year of publication, etc.

In my opinion, the most useful feature is the full text search, for which you use the abbreviation *ft* for full text. This allows Citavi to search the text of the file. I've already mentioned that Citavi can read this using OCR. Of course, this only works if you have saved a file for a title - but this is automatically the case if you have added the title using drag & drop. Alternatively, you can also link a PDF file on your computer to the reference in Citavi.

p//remain in PowerPoint

You can also use wildcards for your search terms.

"?" functions as a placeholder for ONE letter, "*" functions as a placeholder for several or no letters.

This means that you can find names regardless of the spelling.

[CORRECT:] This only works when searching the metadata, not for full-text searches.

You can also use relational operators such as <, >, <=, >=, = because Citavi recognizes text in the year-month-tag format as a date.

You can use this search query to display all titles published after 2014.

And even logical operators such as AND, OR, NOT are usable. However, you must ensure that the brackets are placed correctly here.

q//show Citavi

Now live again.

You can find the quick search and the advanced search here at the top under the magnifying glass symbol or with the usual key combination Ctrl+F.

In the quick search, you can enter search terms exactly as I've just shown you. There are other ways to search for references in Citavi, but they offer fewer functions, so it's best to always use the quick search.

I have prepared a sample request for this.

r//remain in Citavi GUI

"sample" searches all fields, i.e. finds both the author and the title, as well as occurrences in the abstract etc.

In the "Results for your search query" section, you can see that hits were found in 5 titles. If you select one in each case, you will see under "Details of the selected reference" that "sample" was found in the title. Or here, for example, in the abstract or in the author field.

The "Apply found titles as selection" button also displays the titles of the search result in the title list on the side of the project view, just like when importing.

"t: sample" only finds the headline, not the author or other fields, which are now only two articles.

Below you can see that both search results have "sample" in the title.

"t: sample AND d: > 1995" only finds one of the two articles because the other was published in 1991.

Here you can see that Citavi has taken into account what is in the "Title" field and in which year the title was published.

[INCORRECT:] "ft: sampl*" with a wildcard at the end of the word finds all linked PDF files that contain "sampling" or "samples" or "sampler", for example.

[CORRECT:] "ft: sampl*" with wildcard at the end of the word does not find any files, although "sampling" or "samples" or "sampler" is certainly included somewhere. Here you can see that the combination of wildcards and full text search does not work, so we have 0 search results. "sampl*" with a literal asterisk would be interpreted as a hit.

Unfortunately, Citavi doesn't display a preview for full-text searches, so the results are not highlighted. At least you know which references are worth looking at more closely and perhaps starting a search in another program.

This gives you many different options for searching through your collected literature.

SUMMARY SECTION:

That's it for getting started with Citavi.

I hope I was able to show you how many functions Citavi has and how you can use them for reference management.

Notes for researchers:

- Paragraphs marked as **[CORRECT:]** only appeared in the correct video tutorial, while paragraphs marked as **[INCORRECT:]** only appeared in the erroneous tutorial.
- Creating the erroneous video material for the **[INCORRECT:]** sections requires editing the footage manually, as these interactions are impossible in the software.
- Subsections of the videos are enumerated by letters and marked in **green**.
- Comments in gray describe what should be shown in the video while the narration is recorded.